

Syntax, Phylogenetics, and Language Contact

Eve Canning

University of Cambridge

Abstract. Language histories are often considered in terms of genetic relationships, which are often represented using phylogenetic trees. Traditionally, these relationships have been uncovered through the application of the comparative method to sets of cognate lexical items, with only a minor focus on morphological evidence and virtually no consideration given to syntax. More recently, computational methods have been employed for the inference of phylogenies; however, most work has focused on vocabulary cognacy. The Parametric Comparison Method (PCM; described by Longobardi & Guardiano, 2017), by contrast, uses a set of syntactic parameters which account for cross-linguistic variations to generate syntax-based phylogenies. To explore whether evidence of language contact — a secondary concern in previous PCM work — can be found in syntactic phylogenies generated using the PCM, I created a novel parametric database through the combination of Ceolin et al.’s (2021) nominal database and Baker and Roberts’ (In prep.) clausal database. I examined phylogenies generated from this database for their adherence to traditional phylogenies and for evidence of language contact leading to syntactic transfer in the histories of Celtic, Germanic, and Romance. My findings suggest that parametric syntactic phylogenies can provide evidence of language contact, and this is exemplified by a case study involving Afrikaans and English. However, contact effects are subtle and require careful examination of phylogenies and individual parameter settings. I argue that models of linguistic history, including those based on syntax, should account for language, as language contact is an essential component of the story of any speech community.

Keywords: historical linguistics; phylogenetics; syntax

1 Introduction

1.1 Issues in Linguistic Subgrouping

Traditional approaches to linguistic subgrouping have been grounded in the comparative method — see Fox (1995) for an overview — and have generally placed the greatest emphasis on evidence from the lexical-phonological domain. In particular, Campbell and Poser (2008, p. 172) note that evidence from sound changes represents ‘a staple of traditional approaches to determining language families’. This can be contrasted with what Campbell and Poser term ‘grammatical’ evidence, harder to interpret and therefore less of a staple in subgrouping endeavours. Where they do address the use of grammatical evidence, Campbell and Poser deal primarily (pp. 162-224) with morphological evidence, as opposed to evidence from syntax. This can presumably be attributed to the very sparse use of syntactic evidence in linguistic subgrouping as a whole — Clackson (2022, p. 23) notes, for instance, that ‘[i]n the Indo-European language family, little use has been made of syntactic changes for subgrouping’.

Although phylogenetic trees are undoubtedly useful, there are a number of issues concerning the relationship between reconstructed linguistic history (including phylogenies) and real but unattested linguistic history, as observed by Clackson (2022). The tree model assumes that the diversification always occurs following the split of a single speech community into multiple groups which subsequently fall out of touch. Furthermore, it assumes a single, uniform proto-language. Both of these are idealisations. The latter assumption is problematic on uniformitarian grounds (see Roberts, 2017) — there exists today no

language which does not exhibit some form of social or geographic variation, and it follows that no such language existed in the past. Counterexamples to the former assumption are myriad throughout history (see, for example, Dance (2016) on contact between Old Norse and Old English). Therefore, an approach which integrates the insights of the phylogenetic tree with an understanding of language contact is desirable.

The work of Neureiter et al. (2022) represents one attempt at this integration through the incorporation of reconstructed contact events into a computationally generated phylogenetic tree. Their work is, however, focused on the lexical domain. Transfer in the lexical domain is, however, only one of several possible outcomes of language contact. Thomason and Kaufman (1988, pp. 74-75) conceive of transfer in terms of a ‘borrowing scale’, where ‘casual contact’ is expected to lead only to lexical borrowing, but ‘[v]ery strong cultural pressure’ may enable the borrowing of any aspect of language, including major aspects of morphosyntax. Syntactic borrowing is not necessarily as easy to identify as lexical borrowing, although Bowerman (2008) attempts to enumerate some indicators. She nonetheless ‘highlights the importance of using complementary methods’ (p. 18). I argue that these complementary methods should include syntactic phylogenetic reconstruction. The comparison of syntactic phylogenies (the construction of which does not involve the removal of potential transfers) to lexical and phonological phylogenies (which do exclude suspected transfers) may reveal instances of transfer.

1.2 Parametric Comparison

Although lexical approaches to subgrouping and reconstruction are invaluable tools, they are not without limitations imposed by the ease of lexical borrowing and the nature of sound change. Therefore, the development of a method to achieve these goals with reference to other aspects of language may be a profitable goal. Longobardi, Guardiano, and their associates have worked to establish a method for syntactic comparison and reconstruction on the basis of syntactic parameters — the Parametric Comparison Method (PCM). Parametric approaches to syntax characterise cross-linguistic syntactic variation in terms of binary parameters which may have a ‘positive’ or ‘negative’ setting. Longobardi and Guardiano (2017, p. 249) suggest that because parameters are discrete variables, they ‘lend themselves to precise calculations’, enabling quantitative analyses which are not possible using the ‘classical’ comparative method. Furthermore, they argue that parameters are drawn from a universal list (although see Biberauer & Roberts, 2017) and can therefore be used to compare any group of languages, discarding the required prior knowledge of genetic affiliation inherent in many other methods of syntactic reconstruction. Note that parameters, or parameter settings, are not cognates. A parameter setting may be expressed through some element of morphology with associated phonological material (e.g., inflectional person marking on verbs), or through movement, without any overt phonological material (e.g., WH-movement). Where there is no phonological material, it is difficult to assert that a given piece of syntax (i.e., a parameter setting) has been transferred from another language — there is no clear syntactic analogue to the violations of Neogrammarian sound change regularity which mark out lexical transfers. Therefore, the discarding of suspected borrowings which forms part of the lexical-phonological comparative method is not part of the PCM.

The PCM is successful at returning phylogenies which generally resemble those constructed through traditional methods and through vocabulary-based computational methods. The results of Ceolin et al. (2021), who employ nominal parameters, include the successful identification of Indo-European within a broader sample of languages. Ceolin et al. (2020), using the same dataset, return a tree which shows a full internal articulation of Indo-European, including all conventional subgroups represented in the sample.

Baker and Roberts (In prep.; henceforth B&R) apply the PCM to a set of clausal parameters, generating a phylogeny which identifies Indo-European from a broader sample of languages and generally (although not perfectly) identifies conventional subgroups within Indo-European. It remains to be seen, however, how the combination of nominal and clausal parametric data may improve the accuracy of phylogenetic trees. No study has yet collated these data, and in doing so I will be able to provide a more complete overview of the historical signal present in syntax.

An important principle introduced by Ceolin et al. (2020, p. 14) is the ‘Homology Conjecture’. This states that ‘[s]yntactic and lexical histories provide the same evolutionary topologies once interference is equally taken into account’. This is significant because, as mentioned above, the traditional comparative method and other methods for lexical phylogeny crucially involve discarding suspected cases of linguistic transfer in the dataset. The PCM includes no such step. We should therefore expect to find no effects of language contact in lexical phylogenies (interference is ‘taken into account’ before the tree is made); and where syntactic phylogenies differ from lexical ones, we may infer that this is an instance of interference which must now be taken into account.

1.3 Research Aims

As suggested by the above, there are gaps in literature at the intersection of syntactic reconstruction, linguistic phylogenetics, and language contact. This study represents a first effort to explore these gaps by examining the topology of phylogenetic trees generated from a combined dataset of parameters relating to the nominal and clausal domains and examining them for potential evidence of language contact through the application of the Homology Conjecture. Particular attention will be paid in the wider study to the Celtic, Romance, and Germanic languages, in order to enable direct comparison with Neureiter et al. (2022), and this paper will focus on a case study within the Germanic languages.

2 Methodology

2.1 Sources of Data

The data used in this study are drawn from two sources. The first is the set of 94 nominal parameters with settings in 58 languages assembled by Ceolin et al. (2021), available in the digital supplementary information to that paper. The choice of this set of nominal parameters is discussed in §2.2. The second is the set of 87 clausal parameters with settings in 36 languages assembled by B&R. I combined these to create a database of 181 parameters in the 32 languages common to both datasets, which are as follows (note that all groupings listed below, and all subsequent references to ‘conventional’ etc. groupings, follow the groupings in Comrie, 1987).

Table 1: *The 32 languages sampled in the combined nominal/clausal parametric database*

Language	Conventional Family (Subgroup)
Afrikaans	Indo-European (Germanic)
Arabic	Semitic (Central Semitic)
Cantonese	Sino-Tibetan (Sinitic)

Danish	Indo-European (Germanic)
Dutch	Indo-European (Germanic)
English	Indo-European (Germanic)
Estonian	Uralic (Finnic)
Finnish	Uralic (Finnic)
French	Indo-European (Romance)
German	Indo-European (Germanic)
Greek	Indo-European (Hellenic)
Hebrew	Semitic (Northwest Semitic)
Hindi/Urdu	Indo-European (Indo-Iranian)
Hungarian	Uralic (Ugric)
Icelandic	Indo-European (Germanic)
Irish	Indo-European (Celtic)
Italian	Indo-European (Romance)
Japanese	Japonic
Kazakh	Turkic (Kipchak)
Korean	Koreanic
Malagasy	Austronesian (Western Malayo-Polynesian)
Mandarin	Sino-Tibetan (Sinitic)
Norwegian	Indo-European (Germanic)
Polish	Indo-European (Slavic)
Portuguese	Indo-European (Romance)
Romanian	Indo-European (Romance)
Russian	Indo-European (Slavic)
SerBo-Croatian	Indo-European (Slavic)
Slovenian	Indo-European (Slavic)
Spanish	Indo-European (Romance)
Turkish	Turkic (Oghuz)
Welsh	Indo-European (Celtic)

Note the overrepresentation of certain families in the sample; this may ‘normalise’ certain parameter settings and ‘exoticise’ those languages which display the opposite setting, even in cases where a representative survey of the world’s languages would show that this opposite setting is cross-linguistically more frequent.

In addition to the 32-language database, a separate database of the 7 Germanic, 5 Romance, and 2 Celtic languages was created. This was done to enable the creation of phylogenies involving only these three subgroups, for the sake of direct comparison to Neureiter et al. (2022).

2.2 Format of Data

The parameters represented in the dataset take the form of answers to questions such as the example below.

Table 2: Baker and Roberts' (In prep., p. 62) diagnostic question for P_{V1}

Parameter	Diagnostic(s)
P_{V1} (VGP) Grammaticalised Person in EP(V)	Does the language show agreement for person within the clause?

A negative answer is coded as [-] and represents the ‘default’ setting of the parameter (Crisma, Guardiano & Longobardi, 2020, p. 112); a positive answer is coded as [+] and represents a non-default (usually marked) parameter setting. Crisma, Guardiano and Longobardi (2020) argue that parameters should, in theoretical models, be set wholly on the basis of positive evidence, without recourse to negative evidence. Negative parameter settings are part of the ‘initial state of the mind’ (p.112). Many parameters are connected by implicational relationships, in which parameter Y may only be positive if parameter X is also positive. A negative setting for parameter X entails a negative setting for parameter Y. For example, B&R’s P_{V4} (PCV — Φ -feature checking on V) asks whether morphological agreement with the person/number of the subject is realised on V. A number of languages in the sample, however, do not show person or number agreement in the clause (they have negative settings for P_{V1} (VGP) and P_{V2} (VGN)). These languages therefore cannot have a positive setting for P_{V4} — they cannot realise person/number agreement with the subject on V:

(1) <i>Ek werk. / Hy werk. / Ons werk.</i> I work / He work / We work 'I work.' / 'He works.' / 'We work.' (Donaldson, 1993, p. 217) [-] P_{V1} (VGP), [-] P_{V2} (VGN) → [-] P_{V4} (PCV)	(AFRIKAANS)
(1) <i>Rén lái le.</i> Person come PFV/CRS 'The person has come.' / 'The people have come.' (Li and Thompson, 1981, p. 20) [-] P_{V1} (VGP), [-] P_{V2} (VGN) → [-] P_{V4} (PCV) [-] P_{N1} (FGM — Grammaticalised morphology)	(MANDARIN)

These ‘implicational’ parameter settings which are predictable on the basis of an earlier parameter setting are coded in the database as [0]. In rare cases, an informant may be unable to determine the status of a given parameter in their language. In these cases, the parameter is coded as [?].

2.3 Methods

The phylogenetic trees in this study were assembled using two distance-based methods for phylogenetic inference. The first step in distance-based methods is the assembly of a distance matrix, which contains the pairwise Jaccard distance between every language in the dataset. This is calculated as follows, after Ceolin et al. (2020, p. 5):

$$\Delta Jaccard(A, B) = \frac{(N_{\bar{+}} + N_{\pm})}{(N_{\bar{+}} + N_{\pm} + N_{++})}$$

where N_{XY} is the number of instances where language A has parameter setting X and language B has Y. As observed in §2.1., $[-]$ represents the default setting of the parameter, and I therefore follow Ceolin et al. in treating A/B pairings as follows.

Table 3: The treatment of various parameter setting pairings in the calculation of pairwise distances between languages

Pair type	Counted as
$[-]/[+], [+]/[-]$	Difference
$[+]/[+]$	Identity
$[-]/[-]$	Disregarded
$[0]/[X], [X]/[0]$	Disregarded
$[?]/[X], [X]/[?]$	Disregarded

Once a distance matrix has been assembled, a variety of algorithms can be used to construct phylogenies. I employed two: the Unweighted Pair Group method with Arithmetic Mean (henceforth UPGMA) and Neighbour-Joining. The UPGMA and Neighbour-Joining phylogenies were both generated using the programme NEIGHBOR. Following B&R, the UPGMA phylogenies were visualised as rooted trees using the programme DRAWGRAM, while the Neighbour-Joining phylogenies were visualised as unrooted trees using the programme DRAWTREE. All three programmes are part of the PHYLIP package (Felsenstein, 2005). See Goldstein (2020) for analysis of some advantages and drawbacks of each algorithm.

3 Results

The results of the distance calculations and subsequent phylogenetic analysis can be more readily represented in a number of ways. The simplest of these is a colour-coded heatmap presentation of the distance matrices, where low distances are represented in shades of red and high distances in shades of blue, as below.

Figure 1: Heatmap visualisation of the combined nominal and clausal syntactic distances between the complete sample of 32 languages, with distances closer to the minimum of 0 in red and distances closer to the maximum of 0.744 in blue.

	English	Afrikaans	Dutch	German	Norwegian	Danish	Icelandic	French	Italian	Spanish	Portuguese	Romanian	Welsh	Irish
English	0	0.305085	0.278689	0.348485	0.3050847	0.263158	0.343284	0.446154	0.432836	0.344262	0.4	0.452055	0.305085	0.372881
Afrikaans	0.305085	0	0.278689	0.296875	0.3064516	0.266667	0.385714	0.462687	0.485714	0.446154	0.4492754	0.450704	0.476923	0.53125
Dutch	0.278689	0.278689	0	0.15873	0.25	0.224138	0.289855	0.338462	0.343284	0.338462	0.3529412	0.361111	0.393939	0.4375
German	0.348485	0.296875	0.15873	0	0.2698413	0.274194	0.231884	0.352941	0.333333	0.333333	0.3188406	0.295775	0.393939	0.396825
Norwegian	0.305085	0.306452	0.25	0.269841	0	0.186441	0.257576	0.387097	0.390625	0.377049	0.4	0.338235	0.435484	0.423729
Danish	0.263158	0.266667	0.224138	0.274194	0.1864407	0	0.292308	0.403226	0.380952	0.393443	0.40625	0.38806	0.435484	0.47541
Icelandic	0.343284	0.385714	0.289855	0.231884	0.2575758	0.292308	0	0.405405	0.4	0.318841	0.3287671	0.3625	0.323529	0.363636
French	0.446154	0.462687	0.338462	0.352941	0.3870968	0.403226	0.405405	0	0.166667	0.238806	0.2205882	0.283784	0.38806	0.349206
Italian	0.432836	0.485714	0.343284	0.333333	0.390625	0.380952	0.4	0.166667	0	0.208955	0.1641791	0.232877	0.405797	0.363636
Spanish	0.344262	0.446154	0.338462	0.333333	0.3770492	0.393443	0.318841	0.238806	0.208955	0	0.109375	0.28	0.318182	0.378788
Portuguese	0.4	0.449275	0.352941	0.318841	0.4	0.40625	0.328767	0.220588	0.164179	0.109375	0	0.289474	0.343284	0.338462
Romanian	0.452055	0.450704	0.361111	0.295775	0.3382353	0.38806	0.3625	0.283784	0.232877	0.28	0.2894737	0	0.405405	0.4
Welsh	0.305085	0.476923	0.393939	0.393939	0.4354839	0.435484	0.323529	0.38806	0.405797	0.318182	0.3432836	0.405405	0	0.166667
Irish	0.372881	0.53125	0.4375	0.396825	0.4237288	0.47541	0.363636	0.349206	0.363636	0.378788	0.3384615	0.4	0.166667	0

Figure 2: Heatmap visualisation of the combined nominal and clausal syntactic distances between the sample of 14 Celtic, Germanic, and Romance languages, with distances closer to the minimum of 0 in red and distances closer to the maximum of 0.531 in blue.

The UPGMA algorithm produced a phylogeny, visualised as a rooted tree using DRAWGRAM, which in large part agrees with traditional linguistic groupings. This is shown in Figure 3. The UPGMA tree generated from the restricted Celtic/Germanic/Romance sample did not differ from this phylogeny, and has been omitted for space.

Figure 3: UPGMA phylogeny from the combined nominal and clausal syntactic distances between the complete sample of 32 languages.

In the non-rooted tree produced using the Neighbour-Joining algorithm and visualised using DRAWTREE, the Indo-European, Semitic, Turkic, Uralic, and Sinitic families all emerge. Celtic forms a subgroup with Germanic, although there is a large distance between the groups. Slavic and Greek form a subgroup with Romance, and Hindi/Urdu is the most peripheral member of Indo-European. Turkic clusters with the ‘eastern’ languages of the sample rather than with Uralic, as it did in the UPGMA phylogeny. This is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: *Neighbour-Joining phylogeny from the combined nominal and clausal syntactic distances between the complete sample of 32 languages.*

In the restricted-sample unrooted tree, Celtic, Germanic, and Romance form three distinct groups. Celtic has a long branch length and is distinct from the other two subgroups. Germanic and Romance show approximately the same branch length, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: *Neighbour-Joining phylogeny from the combined nominal and clausal syntactic distances between the sample of 14 Celtic/Germanic/Romance languages.*

4 Case Study

Although the results presented in Section 3 are, on the whole, in line with the findings of established work on linguistic subgrouping, there are a number of discrepancies. Among the most notable of these is the tendency of Afrikaans and English to form a unique subgroup (seen most clearly in Figures 3 and 5). This is at odds with the findings of both computational phylogenetic studies employing lexical data (Chang et al., 2015; Neureiter et al., 2022), which group Afrikaans with languages such as Dutch and Flemish, and traditional assessments of Germanic subgrouping such as Hawkins (1987, p. 68), who refers simply to ‘Dutch (including Afrikaans)’. The topology of the syntactic tree diverges from that of lexical trees; therefore, the Homology Conjecture suggests that there are interference effects which must be taken into account.

The histories of both Afrikaans and English are known to involve extensive language contact, probably more extensive than any other Germanic language in the sample. Van der Wouden and Muysken

(2012, p. 3) outline the contact history of Afrikaans, starting in the 17th century, which includes contact between Dutch, Khoekhoe (spoken by indigenous populations in the Cape province), Malagasy, Malay, Indo-Portuguese Creole (all three spoken by slaves brought to the colony), and English (following the occupation of the colony by the British). Contact in the history of English, meanwhile, occurs over a longer time period, involving the Celtic varieties present in the British Isles upon the arrival of Germanic speakers, the Old Norse of 9th-11th century settlers, and Norman French following the invasion of 1066.

In order to examine whether the effects of language contact are causing Afrikaans and English to diverge from the rest of Germanic in the syntactic phylogenies of Section 3, it will be useful to identify exactly which parameter settings distinguish the languages. The following seven parameters differ in Afrikaans and/or English compared to the majority setting in Germanic.

Table 4: *Notable points of variation in the parameter settings of Afrikaans and/or English compared to the rest of the Germanic languages in the sample.*

Parameter	Afrikaans	English	Other Germanic languages
P _V 13 (TCV — Tense-checking V)	[-]	[+]	[+]
P _V 30 (NNI — Null prohibitive)	[-]	[-]	[+] except for Danish
P _V 39 (AXS — Auxiliary split)	[-]	[-]	[+] in Dutch, German, and Danish
P _V 68 (DAT — Dative Case)	[-]	[-]	[+] except for Norwegian and Danish
P _V 77 (QCV — Q-checking V)	[+]	[-]	[-]
P _V 83 (NMU — Multiple negation)	[+]	[-]	[-]
P _V 86 (INC — Noun incorporation)	[+]	[-]	[-]

I will briefly examine each of these parameters in turn to determine whether the divergent settings of Afrikaans/English can be attributed to language contact. Note that PV77 (QCV — ‘Are interrogatives marked by bound morphology on V?’) has been greyed out in Table 4 because it was found to be an error in the dataset (Biberauer, p.c.). Afrikaans does not show any bound morphology on V, including in interrogatives. However, the correction of this parameter setting did not lead to any changes in the trees generated from the dataset.

PV13 (TCV — Tense-checking V) asks whether Tense ‘may [...] be realised just on V’ (B&R, p. 65). Afrikaans is the only language in the sample to have a [-] setting for this parameter. Past and future meaning are both expressed periphrastically:

(3) Ek het gewerk. (AFRIKAANS)

I have worked

'I worked.' / 'I have worked.' / 'I had worked.'

(4) Ek sal dit doen as ek tyd het.

I will it do if I time have

'I'll do it if I have the time.'

Donaldson (1993, pp. 217, 235)

[-] PV13

The negative setting of this parameter is clearly an Afrikaans innovation — Tense on V was found in Middle Dutch (van Kerckvoorde, 1992, p. 89) as well as in modern Dutch. The lack of morphological tense expression on the lexical verb is reminiscent of the invariant verb forms of many creole languages (as described by Holm, 2012, p. 174). De Kleine (1997) argues that the loss of the morphology expressing tense on the verb, and the taking over of this function by periphrastic constructions, suggest significant contact-induced restructuring in the history of Afrikaans.

PV30 (NNI — Null prohibitive) asks whether bare or non-finite verbs in a negative context may have imperative force. Compare the following sentences in Italian and Dutch ([+] PV30) to their English ([-] PV30) translation:

- | | | |
|-----------------|----------------|-----------|
| (5) <i>Non</i> | <i>fumare.</i> | (ITALIAN) |
| NEG | smoke.INF | |
| 'Do not smoke.' | | |
| (6) <i>Niet</i> | <i>roken.</i> | (DUTCH) |
| NEG | smoke.INF | |
| 'Do not smoke.' | | |

The positive setting for this parameter in the broader Indo-European language family is widespread, but does not characterise any particular subgroup: [+] and [-] settings are found for this parameter in every well-represented Indo-European subgroup. The negative settings in English and Afrikaans therefore probably need not be explained through language contact.

PV39 (AXS — Auxiliary split) determines whether auxiliaries in periphrastic constructions vary on the basis of some predictable factor other than voice (for example, a HAVE/BE split periphrastic perfect constructions). The only languages with a positive setting for this parameter are Dutch, German, Danish, French, Italian, and Romanian. These languages are associated with the core of Haspelmath's (2001) Standard Average European (SAE) Sprachbund. The presence of a 'HAVE-perfect', a construction which commonly exhibits an auxiliary split in these languages, is one of Haspelmath's (1998) 11 defining features of SAE. Its development and/or retention, and the retention of a HAVE/BE split in many languages of Western Europe may be a result of sustained language contact. However, the split was lost in English, another language in the core SAE area. The use of *be* as a perfect auxiliary persisted in English as late as the 19th century (McFadden, 2017; van Gelderen, 2014, p. 219). McFadden and Alexiadou (2010) do not relate the loss of the construction (which they do not analyse as structurally identical to the HAVE-perfect) to language contact, but to language-internal factors. Conradie (2015) does not directly relate the loss of the BE-perfect in Afrikaans to language contact, instead linking it to factors such as the loss of the preterite, creating a less direct association with language contact.

PV68 (DAT — Dative Case) concerns the presence or absence of a dative case assigned to Goals/Recipients in double object constructions. In Afrikaans and English, the distinction between accusative and dative has been lost even in the pronominal systems (where it is retained marginally in, e.g., French), which instead distinguish only between subject (e.g., English *he*, Afrikaans *hy*) and object/oblique (e.g., English *him*, Afrikaans *hom*). Already in Old English there was significant syncretism between the accusative and the dative in, for example, the declension of weak nouns, as well as in the personal pronouns:

Table 5: *Selected Old English personal pronouns in the accusative and dative, after Mitchell and Robinson (2011, pp. 18-19)*

	Singular		Plural	
	ACC	DAT	ACC	DAT
1	<i>mē, meċ</i>	<i>mē</i>	<i>ūs, ūsic</i>	<i>ūs</i>
2	<i>þē, þēċ</i>	<i>þē</i>	<i>ēow, ēowic</i>	<i>ēow</i>
3	<i>hine (M)</i>	<i>him (M)</i>	<i>hīe, hī</i>	<i>him, heom</i>

Phonological changes such as the merger and loss of final /m/ and /n/ (Lass, 1992, p. 65) and the loss of final /ə/ (Lass, 1992, p.79) and analogical pressures eventually led to the loss of a distinct dative in English. Some of this paradigmatic simplification may be attributable to contact with speakers of Old Norse (see, e.g., van Gelderen, 2014, p. 98). The input system for Afrikaans probably already had minimal distinct dative marking. The Middle Dutch accusative and dative personal pronouns, for example, were formally identical except in the neuter singular (van Kerckvoorde, 1992, pp. 65, 75). Language contact in the history of Afrikaans may have encouraged the loss of a distinct dative, but this was clearly already underway, and the distinction is marginal in modern Dutch.

PV83 (NMU — Multiple negation) concerns whether negative concord is permitted in a language. Afrikaans is the only modern Germanic language which allows negative concord:

- (7) Hy is nie moeg nie. (AFRIKAANS)
 He is NEG tired NEG
 'He is not tired.'
- (8) Hy is nooit moeg nie.
 He is never tired NEG
 'He is never tired.'
- Biberauer and Zeijlstra (2012, pp. 355-356)
 [+] P_v83 (NMU)

Compare to English:

- (9) *He is never not tired.*

In standard varieties this requires the positive reading 'he is always tired'. There are two theories regarding the rise of multiple negation in Afrikaans, reflecting arguments about the overall origins of Afrikaans. Either it is descended from a feature of 17th century dialectal Dutch, or it was taken over from a Dutch-based creole or pidgin spoken in the Cape province. The frequency of negative concord in creole languages is noted by Holm (2012, pp. 195-197), although he notes that these structures are often permissible in source languages. Den Besten (1986) rejects the notion that Afrikaans multiple negation is descended from dialectal Dutch, and endorses the contact argument.

PV88 (INC — Noun incorporation) asks 'May nominal arguments incorporate into the verb?' (B&R, p. 81). This is a feature particularly characteristic of polysynthetic languages, and Afrikaans is the only

language in the sample with a positive setting for PV88. Non-finite verbs are briefly discussed in Ponelis (1993, p. 579) Bare nouns may be productively incorporated into (only) non-finite verbs:

- (10) *Ons gaan DVDkyk.* (AFRIKAANS)
We go DVD-watch
'We are going to watch a DVD.'
[+] **Pv88 (INC)**

This is distinct from:

- (11) *Ons gaan 'n DVD kyk.*
We go a DVD watch
'We are going to watch a DVD.'

Barrie and Spreng (2009) argue that noun incorporation may be found in German, and Booij (2009) argues for 'quasi-incorporation' in Dutch. Basilico (2016) analyses a similar construction in Frisian, which allows not only non-finite but also finite verbs to be formed in this way. He argues, however, that this construction should be analysed as a 'more typologically appropriate instance of synthetic compounding' rather than as true noun incorporation. This suggests that the [-] settings for this parameter in Germanic languages such as German and Dutch are to some degree a question of analysis, and the construction's presence in Afrikaans is not necessarily the result of language contact (although closer examination of the relative productivity/frequency of such constructions in Afrikaans vs. German, Dutch, etc., may reveal differences which would require explanation).

Nonetheless, many of the parameter settings which set English and Afrikaans apart from the other Germanic languages can be related to the intensive contact which these languages have undergone throughout their histories. While this case study draws upon (more-or-less) known instances of language contact, it suggests that divergences between syntactic phylogenies and lexical ones truly can be indicative of interference arising from contact.

5 Conclusion

The case study of Afrikaans and English presented above showcases the potential of the PCM as a method for exploring potential instances of language contact and its effects. It is clear, however, that syntactic phylogenies can serve only as a signpost or rough guide towards contact events, and the researcher cannot be absolved of the need for careful, context-sensitive, fine-grained work. While the 'headline' aspect of the PCM is its use in generating phylogenies, in light of the above it should also be recognised that much power lies in having a set of cross-linguistically comparable syntactic parameters, which enables work such as that in Section 4.

Why, however, does it matter whether we can incorporate language contact into models of linguistic history? In attempting to construct phylogenies for the languages of the world, we are implicitly attempting to construct narratives about our origins — and the origins of others. A model of linguistic divergence which takes the form of a binary branching tree suggests a narrative in which peoples became sharply differentiated from one another, any similarities between them the relic of a distant shared past. This narrative is, as discussed in Section 1.1, untrue. A model of syntactic phylogeny and reconstruction which

accepts the notion of syntactic transfer and seeks out instances of language contact promotes a conceptualisation of human history which is less rigidly divided and more full of collaboration, conquest, and all other kinds of contact.

6 References

- Baker, J., & Roberts, I. (in prep.). *Extending parametric comparison: Preliminary results*.
- Barrie, M., & Spreng, B. (2009). Noun incorporation and the progressive in German. *Lingua*, 119, 374–388.
- Basilico, D. (2016). Noun incorporation in Frisian. *University of Pennsylvania Working Papers in Linguistics*, 22(1), 21–30.
- den Besten, H. (1986). Double negation and the genesis of Afrikaans. In P. Muysken & N. Smith (Eds.), *Substrata versus universals in creole genesis* (pp. 185–230). Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Biberauer, T., & Zeijlstra, H. (2012). Negative concord in Afrikaans: Filling a typological gap. *Journal of Semantics*, 29, 345–371. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jos/ffr013>
- Biberauer, T., & Roberts, I. (2017). Parameter setting. In A. Ledgeway & I. Roberts (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of historical syntax* (pp. 134–162). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Booij, G. (2009). A constructional analysis of quasi-incorporation in Dutch. *Gengo Kenkyu: Journal of the Linguistic Society of Japan*, 135, 5–27.
- Bowern, C. (2008). Syntactic change and syntactic borrowing in generative grammar. In G. Ferraresi & M. Goldbach (Eds.), *Principles of syntactic reconstruction* (pp. 187–216). Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Campbell, L., & Poser, W. J. (2008). *Language classification: History and method*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ceolin, A., Guardiano, C., Irimia, M. A., & Longobardi, G. (2020). Formal syntax and deep history. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, Article 2489. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.544853>
- Ceolin, A., Guardiano, C., Longobardi, G., Irimia, M. A., Bortolussi, L., & Sgarro, A. (2021). At the boundaries of syntactic prehistory. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 376(1824), Article 20200197. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2020.0197>
- Chang, W., Hall, D., Cathcart, C., & Garrett, A. (2015). Ancestry-constrained phylogenetic analysis supports the Indo-European steppe hypothesis. *Language*, 91(1), 194–244.
- Clackson, J. (2022). Methodology in linguistic subgrouping. In T. Olander (Ed.), *The Indo-European language family: A phylogenetic perspective* (pp. 18–32). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Comrie, B. (Ed.). (1987). *The world's major languages*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Conradie, C. J. (2015). The loss of BE as a mutative marker in Afrikaans. In M. L. Kotin & R. Whitt (Eds.), *To be or not to be? The verbum substantivum from synchronic, diachronic and typological perspectives* (pp. 251–278). Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Crisma, P., Guardiano, C., & Longobardi, G. (2020). Syntactic diversity and language learnability. *Studi e Saggi Linguistici*, 58(2), 99–130.
- Dance, R. (2016). North Sea currents: Old English and Old Norse in comparison and in contact. In P. Szarmach (Ed.), *Books most needful to know: Contexts for the study of Anglo-Saxon England* (pp. 265–304). Kalamazoo: Medieval Institute Publications, Western Michigan University.

- Donaldson, B. C. (1993). *A grammar of Afrikaans*. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Felsenstein, J. (2005). *PHYLIP (Phylogeny Inference Package) version 3.6* [Computer software]. Seattle: Department of Genome Sciences, University of Washington.
- Fox, A. (1995). *Linguistic reconstruction: An introduction to theory and method*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Goldstein, D. M. (2020). Indo-European phylogenetics in R. **Indo-European Linguistics*, 8*, 110–180. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22125892-00801007>
- Haspelmath, M. (1998). How young is Standard Average European? *Language Sciences*, 20(3), 271–287.
- Haspelmath, M. (2001). The European linguistic area: Standard Average European. In M. Haspelmath, E. König, W. Oesterreicher, & W. Raible (Eds.), *Language typology and language universals* (pp. 1492–1510). Berlin: Walter de Gruyter.
- Hawkins, J. A. (1987). Germanic languages. In B. Comrie (Ed.), *The world's major languages* (pp. 68–76). New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Holm, J. A. (2012). *An introduction to pidgins and creoles*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Håkansson, G., Pienemann, M., & Sayehli, S. (2002). Transfer and typological proximity in the context of second language processing. *Second Language Research*, 18(3), 250–273.
- van Kerckvoorde, C. M. (1992). *An introduction to Middle Dutch*. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- de Kleine, C. (1997). The verb phrase in Afrikaans: Evidence of creolization? In D. Winford & A. K. Spears (Eds.), *The structure and status of pidgins and creoles* (pp. 289–308). Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Lass, R. (1992). Phonology and morphology. In N. Blake (Ed.), *The Cambridge history of the English language: Vol. 2. 1066–1476* (pp. 23–155). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Li, C. N., & Thompson, S. A. (1981). *Mandarin Chinese: A functional reference grammar*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
- Lightfoot, D. (2002). Myths and the prehistory of grammars. *Journal of Linguistics*, 38(1), 113–136.
- Longobardi, G., & Guardiano, C. (2009). Evidence for syntax as a signal of historical relatedness. *Lingua*, 119(11), 1679–1706.
- Longobardi, G., & Guardiano, C. (2017). Phylogenetic reconstruction in syntax: The Parametric Comparison Method. In A. Ledgeway & I. Roberts (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of historical syntax* (pp. 241–272). Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- Longobardi, G., Guardiano, C., Silvestri, G., Boattini, A., & Ceolin, A. (2013). Toward a syntactic phylogeny of modern Indo-European languages. *Journal of Historical Linguistics*, 3(1), 122–152.
- McFadden, T. (2017). On the disappearance of the BE perfect in Late Modern English. *Acta Linguistica Hafniensia*, 49(2), 159–175.
- McFadden, T., & Alexiadou, A. (2010). Perfects, resultatives, and auxiliaries in earlier English. *Linguistic Inquiry*, 41(3), 389–425.
- Mitchell, B., & Robinson, F. C. (2011). *A guide to Old English* (8th ed.). Malden, MA: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Neureiter, N., Ranacher, P., Efrat-Kowalsky, N., Kaiping, G. A., Weibel, R., Widmer, P., & Bouckaert, R. (2022). Detecting contact in language trees: A Bayesian phylogenetic model with horizontal transfer. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 9(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01082-y>
- Ponelis, F. (1993). *The development of Afrikaans*. Frankfurt am Main: Peter Lang.
- Ringe, D. (2006). *From Proto-Indo-European to Proto-Germanic*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Roberts, I. (2017). Uniformitarianism. In A. Ledgeway & I. Roberts (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of historical syntax* (pp. 338–359). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Thomason, S. G., & Kaufman, T. (1988). *Language contact, creolization, and genetic linguistics*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
- van der Wouden, T., & Muysken, P. (2012). Introduction. In T. van der Wouden (Ed.), *Roots of Afrikaans: Selected writings of Hans den Besten* (pp. 1–5). Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- van Gelderen, E. (2014). *A History of the English Language: Revised edition*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.